

Report on research carried out in Iran, June 1970 to October 1971, sponsored by the Gerald Avery Wainwright fund of Oxford University. Unpublished: Ashmolean Archive.

Ollaberry,
Crimmas Hill,
Great Missenden,
Bucks,
5/12/71.

Your Ref: AM/16

Miss. J. Nicholson,

The Gerald Avery Wainwright Near Eastern Archaeological Fund,

The University Registry,

Clarendon Building,

Broad Street,

Oxford, OX1 3BD.

Dear Miss Nicholson,

Your letter of 23 June was received by my Father in England and handed to me when I recently returned from Iran. The copy sent to Iran was probably misdirected from Teheran since I have not received it yet.

My grant from the Gerald Avery Wainwright Near Eastern Archaeological Fund was as I am sure you will remember for a period of fifteen months terminating in October 1971, so writing now I am able to present a report on the whole period during which I held the grant.

I am grateful to the Board of Management of the Fund for their support and would appreciate your placing the enclosed report before the Board of Management when they meet shortly. I would be happy to provide the Board any further information they may require.

Yours sincerely,

A.G. Williamson

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REPORT ON RESEARCH CARRIED OUT IN IRAN JUNE 1970 TO OCTOBER 1971
SUPPORTED BY THE GERALD AVERY WAINWRIGHT FUND OF OXFORD UNIVERSITY.

I was a grantee of the Gerald Avery Wainwright Fund of Oxford University for the period June 1970 to October 1971.

The major part of my research during that period was directed towards the completion of my doctoral thesis for the Dept. of Oriental Studies of Oxford University entitled:

"Archaeological and documentary material for the history and mechanisms of commerce in Southern Iran from the seventh century A.D. to the end of the Portuguese Period."

Archaeological surface survey was continued over a period of four months in 1970-71, and although the Iranian Government would not permit the study of the whole Iranian coast the material collected from over 1200 archaeological sites visited between 1968 and 1971 has proved more than adequate in determining the trends of settlement and the direction of trade for the purposes of my thesis. The most important single result of the latest season of field survey was the mapping of the Sassanian and very early Islamic sites at

Bushehr first visited in 1969, which with a mounded area of 450 hectares are probably the largest concentration of sites of any period anywhere on the Persian coast.

The analysis of pottery and other artefacts found in 1968-71 was delayed by the refusal of the Iranian Government to permit their study at Siraf where they were stored. This forced the transport of almost three tons of pottery and the organisation of alternative study facilities. The analysis of all this material was nevertheless completed in April 1971 and is producing most useful results.

Two of my major occupations during the period of this grant, both of which have proved exceptionally rewarding, were not anticipated in the original application.

In the Summers of 1970 and 1971 I was given the opportunity on behalf of the Harvard Expedition to Tepe Yahya to direct excavations on the Islamic site at Tepe Dasht-i-Deh. Two large and rich stratigraphically sealed groups of artefacts were isolated, associated with the destruction of two architectural levels. Although no coins nor inscriptions were found both groups contained many fine pottery types some of which closely parallel Museum peices with inscribed

*in public + private
man collections*

dates of the 13 c. A.D. for one group and the 14 c. for the other. These centuries are very poorly represented in the excavations at Siraf, and that pottery which hitherto could be dated to the 13 or 14 c. has such a friable fabric that it is rarely preserved on the surface. The excavations at Tepe Dasht-i-Deh are of the greatest importance for establishing the ceramic chronology of Southern Iran in this period and for permitting the closer dating of large quantities of material from surface reconnaissances. Brief reports on the excavations appeared in Iran IX and Iran X (in press). A monograph publication will appear in due course as one of the Papers of the Peabody Museum of Harvard University.

In the Winter of 1970 I was given the opportunity as a guest of the Abu Dhabi Government to investigate the potential for archaeological research on the Arab side of the Gulf in the historic periods. In a six week stay I was able to establish the feasibility of a research project to be carried out on the completion of my thesis. This project for which I have been awarded a Randall-MacIver Studentship at the Queen's College is entitled "Archaeological investigations of pearling and commerce in the Persian Gulf 400 B.C. to 1000 A.D.". This will involve the study of the Hellenistic to Sassanian pottery and shells collected in my survey in Southern Iran, a field survey on the South

shore of the Persian Gulf and a detailed investigation of the origins and history of the pearling industry over the whole Gulf. As I indicated in my application to the Gerald Avery Wainwright Fund it was my discoveries in Southern Iran which led me to attach great importance to the pearling industry in the history of the Persian Gulf and my finds over the last year have tended to confirm this. The Queen's grant will allow me to study the pearling industry of the Gulf at the period during which the great commercial cities which I have studied in the Islamic Period came into being.

The PreHellenistic material found on my survey has not been neglected. It is currently being studied by Miss. M.E. Prickett who plans to conduct additional survey in the Winter of 1972 and present all the material in her doctoral dissertation at Harvard in 1973.

The work at Dasht-i-Deh and in connection with my postdoctoral project have both improved my understanding of my thesis research, but have of course delayed its completion. The thesis is however well under way and will be ready for presentation in Trinity term of 1972. A section (40 pages) is in press for Bostan Chenassi va Honar-e Iran entitled "Persian Gulf Commerce in the Sassanian Period and the first two centuries of Islam."

I am most grateful to the Committee of the Gerald Avery Wainwright Fund for the grant which permitted me to continue my research for the fifteen months June 1970 to October 1971. I hope that in the view of the Committee this has been well spent. I would be very happy to provide any more information or answer any queries the Committee may have.

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Andrew George Williamson.